

THE CONTENT AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF METHODOLOGICAL IMPROVEMENT OF THE DIAGNOSTIC SYSTEM OF PREPARING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION

Khasanova Irodaxon Najmiddin kizi

Doctoral student at Namangan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7895654>

Annotation: This article emphasizes the importance of children's age-related psychophysiology, the creation of optimal conditions for the intellectual development of preschool children, work forms related to preschool education, speech formation, the importance of the neighborhood in the life of a child of this age, and the need to widely use various forms of practical and visual activities of children.

Key words: Mental activity, speech, neighborhood, social, subject.

The formation of an excellent system of training personnel on the basis of the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal values, the achievements of modern culture, economy, science and technology is an important condition for the development of Uzbekistan. Preschool education ensures that the child is healthy, comprehensively developed and formed, instills in him a sense of desire to study, prepares him for regular education. Neighborhoods, public and charitable organizations, international foundations are actively involved in the realization of the goals and objectives of preschool education.

For the development of preschool education, it will be necessary to carry out:

- Priority training of qualified educator and pedagogical personnel;
- Search and introduction of effective psychological and pedagogical methods of preschool education;
- Organizational, psychological, pedagogical and methodological support of the upbringing of children in the family;
- Creation and production of modern educational and methodical manuals, technical means, toys and games;
- Creation of conditions for the upbringing of preschool children from spiritual and moral character on the basis of the rich cultural and historical heritage of the people and universal values;
- Selection of programs of different options for different types of preschool institutions, creation of the possibility of providing a qualified consultation service on all issues of preschool education;

Aims at such tasks as the development of a mechanism for the support and development of a network of preschool and health institutions. It is also said that the regulations on preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan have a special emphasis on preschool education, and preschool education is the primary type of continuing education system and is organized on the basis of the requirements of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on education", the national program for training personnel. Preschool education is carried out in the family and in state and non-state (non-state-owned) preschool educational institutions until the child reaches the age of 6-7 years.

The main tasks of preschool education are defined as:

Raising children from mental and spiritual and moral dignity on the basis of the rich national, cultural historical heritage of the people and universal human resources;

- Formation of feelings of national pride, patriotism in children;
- Formation of the need for knowledge in preschool children, inclinations for learning and their regular preparation for the educational process;
- Development of children's thinking, formation of the skills of independent and free expression of one's own opinion;

Children of the same age, as well as of different ages, can be admitted to groups of children of yasli and preschool age of preschool educational institutions.

The number of children in groups is determined as follows:

From 2 to 3 years old – 15 PCs.

From 3 to 6-7 years old-20 pcs.

15 in different age groups.

The main tasks of education and upbringing of preschool children are to prepare children for regular education on the basis of national and universal values, taking into account their innate abilities, interests, needs and capabilities, from physical, mental and spiritual development. In the process of communicating with adults in a child, the first experiences of moral behavior are formed. The need for communication is an important social need, and an adult is a resource that satisfies this social need. The upbringing of moral feelings and habits is considered such a necessary basis that without it it is impossible to form more complex features of the child's personality, the provision of spiritual perfection, perceptions of the phenomena of the country's social life and a positive attitude towards them.

The basis of humanism, which is contained in the early stages of preschool childhood, is its social orientation in children, which gradually serves as the basis for the formation of public signs of the individual: behavioral habits, attitudes and imaginations. First of all, it is necessary to create in a children's institution the correct style of interaction between adult members of the team. Mutual respect and care, love of work, participation in the political and Labor life of the country – all this should provide the necessary style. It is important to carry out the correct relations of the pedagogical team and parent teams based on the requirements of today. This form of work is formed as a result of the regular work of the MTT with parents, the study of family upbringing experiences. A high level of interaction between adults and children is an obligatory condition for successful moral education.

The content and methods of moral education of preschool children should correspond to the characteristics of children of this age, and it should provide for the process of moral development at the nearest time. For example, if 4-year-old children provide valuable assistance to their peers mainly under the influence of the educator's advice, instructions, then when they turn 5, they should provide such assistance at their discretion. The atmosphere of love, mutual attention, care inherent in the family affects the formation of a child's feeling. Social emotions in which a decision is made in the family are an important basis for the correct moral development of a child from a small age.

"The chinakkam School of Health and Goodwill education is a family; the attitude towards the father, mother, grandmother, grandmother, brothers, sisters is a test of humanity," our scholars say. An important task of the Educator of a preschool educational institution is to explain to parents that they play a special role in the formation of the child's personality, to

help them closely in acquiring the necessary pedagogical knowledge and skills. The role of the neighborhood in ensuring the spiritual maturation of children is also great. The neighborhood is, first of all, a healthy social environment. Public opinion, which has a strong influence here, says that the behavior of the people of the neighborhood regulates their relationship on the basis of justice and spiritual criteria. The neighborhood is made up of people who make up families with different backgrounds, nationalities, clients. Such important tasks as attaching the heads of these families, strengthening them spiritually and materially, raising young people will also be carried out in the neighborhood. Families are united by one community, social group, institution, exactly the neighborhood. They form, cultivate harmony, solidarity, cooperation, empathy, feelings. In the life of every citizen, the Trinity "person-family-neighborhood" is of great importance. This is a kind of system of our oriental lifestyle and, most importantly, an important tool in the fact that a person is immersed in the life of society and becomes a participant in social relations. The faith, decency, orality, conscience, thinking of a person formed in the family will rise further in the neighborhood environment and will lead to the formation of healthy relations in society, harmonizing with the interests of the people, feelings of mutual grace and cooperation.

The system of work on the development of speech in a preschool educational institution. One of the main tasks of a preschool educational institution is to form the correct oral speech of children as a result of mastering the artistic language of their people. This general task consists of the following special tasks: education of the sound culture of speech, enrichment, strengthening and activation of vocabulary, improvement of the grammatical correctness of speech, formation of oral (dialogical) speech, development of fluent speech, education of interest in an artistic word, preparation for teaching literacy. It is necessary to carry out the development of children's speech on the basis of the appropriate program. In this program, the scope of knowledge about the world and the volume of vocabulary, speech skills and skills that should be formed in children at each age stage are defined, which should provide for the upbringing of certain qualities of a person (sociability, sociability, composure). The speech development program is built on a scientific basis, which, with its entire content, is aimed at the comprehensive development of the child's personality. The speech development program takes place in such forms of the child's activity as educational, game, labor and household. Education in the context of public education is the leading tool for the formation of a child's speech.

Teaching the native language is the process of developing children's cognitive abilities with a planned, clear goal, mastering the simplest knowledge about their environment and the appropriate vocabulary, the formation of speech skills and skills. The main form of teaching preschool children is Classes.

The following types of training can be distinguished for didactic purposes:

- training to inform the new material;
- training on strengthening knowledge, skills and skills;
- training on the generalization and systematization of knowledge;
- final training or account check (control) training.

It is recommended to conduct classes on the development of children's speech from 1 to 3 years old in the form of didactic games, ermak Games, stage performances. They should have not only an entertaining tone, but of course an educational one.

The development of speech in children from 3 to 5 years old should have an emotional tone. It is necessary to widely use exhibitionism, game methods and didactic games.

Classes for the development of children's speech from 5 to 7 years old have a specific task – that is, it provides for the preparation of children to study at school.

Formation of the ability to establish educational activities in addition to pedagogical speech tasks in the classes (to be attentive, listen to the pedagogical task, understand and do it clearly, be able to get an idea in front of a children's team, be able to give a simple assessment of the peer's response, etc.) also performs the function.

The role of mental education in preparing children for school education. The acquisition of knowledge of children serves as a resource for them in the development of their mental activity, the acquisition of mental skills and skills, their successful study at school, in preparation for future labor activities. The role of mental education in preparing children for school is great. An important condition is the expansion of the reserve of knowledge, the development of mental activity and independence, good studies at school, preparation for further work activities. It takes a lot of responsibility from the educator to ensure that the child goes to school from the age of 6-7, that mental development is enough to prepare them for school education. At preschool age, knowledge develops at a rapid pace, becomes richer. Speech is formed, cognitive processes are improved, the child acquires the simplest methods of mental activity. Mental activity in children is carried out initially through treatment, then through training, knowledge.

Conclusion. Mental activity in children was carried out initially through treatment, and then through training, games, knowledge. The child will always be among the items, employees. Constantly get acquainted with something, learn something, Hold On, listen to something, in this way the child realizes the world. The surrounding objects and objects affect the sensory organs of their children, analyzers, and intuition is formed. The development of mental skills and abilities in a child, checking the subjects of the simplest methods of activity, highlighting important and non-essential signs in them comparison with other subjects is one of the tasks of mental education for children of preschool age.

References:

1. Maktabgacha ta'lim pedagogikasi (Pedagogika kollejlari uchun o'quv qo'llanma). To'ldirilgan va qayta ishlangan 2-nashri. Toshkent-«ILM ZIYO»-2011.
2. Maktabgacha pedagogika [Matn] darslik / F.R.Qodirova – Xalqaro pedagogika Akademiyasining akademigi, professor, p.f.d., Sh.Q-Toshpulatova - dotsent, N.M.Kayumova - dotsent, M.NA'zamova - Toshkent: Tafakkur nashriyoti, 2019.
3. Kontsepsiia doshkolnoho vospitaniia [The concept of preschool education]. (1989). Doshkolnoe vospitanie – Preschool education, 5 [in Russian].

